
Position: Large Language Model Failures from Hallucination to Homogenization Are Different Facets of Miscalibration

Tiancheng Hu¹ Caiqi Zhang¹ Dirk Hovy^{*2} Nigel Collier^{*1}

Abstract

This position paper argues that diverse failures of Large Language Models (LLMs), from confident hallucinations to collapsed diversity to brittle safety refusals, are best understood as different facets of a single underlying problem: miscalibration. We propose a unified framework organized around four types of miscalibration: *probabilistic* (the model cannot match requested probability distributions), *semantic* (confidence is misaligned with factual correctness), *distributional* (output diversity collapses to stereotypical modes), and *metacognitive* (the model fails to assess its own competence). We argue that foregrounding calibration as a diagnostic lens and evaluation target is essential for building models that are not merely capable, but genuinely reliable. We call for calibration metrics to become a standard part of benchmark reporting, for training paradigms that preserve uncertainty, and for interaction designs that surface model confidence to downstream decision-makers.

1. Introduction

Ask GPT-4o for a random number between 1 and 10, and it will say “7” over 60% of the time, a near-perfect reproduction of a well-documented human cognitive bias known as the *Blue-Seven Phenomenon* (West & Potts, 2025). Ask it how many Rs are in “strawberry,” and it will confidently, incorrectly answer “two.” Ask it to write a story featuring a Black protagonist, and it will pepper the text with shibboleths like “finna” and “chile,” collapsing the diversity of Black American speech into a narrow caricature (Rooein et al., 2025). Ask it what 2+3 equals, and it may spend a thousand tokens “reasoning” before answering 5 (Chen et al., 2025). These failures are typically studied in isolation: probabilistic reasoning, factuality, bias, and efficiency,

¹University of Cambridge ²Bocconi University. Correspondence to: Tiancheng Hu <th656@cam.ac.uk>.

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Figure 1. Four facets of LLM miscalibration. Each facet represents a distinct manifestation of the misalignment between a model’s confidence and reality, from failures in probabilistic reasoning to breakdowns in self-awareness.

respectively. Here, we argue that they are **all symptoms of a single underlying problem: miscalibration**, the systematic misalignment between a model’s confidence and reality. As LLMs are increasingly deployed in high-stakes domains, from medical diagnosis and legal research to financial advising and educational assessment, the ability to trust their outputs becomes essential. Yet trust requires more than capability; it demands reliability, which in turn depends on calibration (Steyvers et al., 2025).

But how do we measure calibration today? Current calibration evaluations of LLMs descend directly from classification metrics, like the Expected Calibration Error (ECE). While valuable, this framing is increasingly insufficient for today’s models. LLMs are no longer merely classifiers; they are generators, simulators, reasoners, creators, and increasingly, autonomous agents. Their calibration failures, therefore, extend far beyond what traditional calibration metrics capture: incorrect multiple-choice answers. This paper offers a unified framework for understanding these broader failures. We organize our argument around four

key areas where miscalibration is both pervasive and under-appreciated:

1. **Probabilistic Miscalibration: The Illusion of Randomness** (§3.1). The model’s failure to generate outputs that faithfully match a requested probability distribution. Example: sampling “7” 60% of the time when asked for a random number between 1 and 10 (*Blue-Seven*).
2. **Semantic Miscalibration: The Confidence-Factuality Gap** (§3.2). The gap between a model’s expressed confidence and the factual or logical correctness of its statements. Example: confidently stating that “strawberry” contains 2 Rs (*strawberry*).
3. **Distributional Miscalibration: The Collapse of Diversity** (§3.3). Collapsing the wide distribution over possible valid outputs into a narrow, high-probability set of clichés. Example: overusing shibboleths when prompted with a Black persona (*finna*).
4. **Metacognitive Miscalibration: The Failure of Self-Awareness** (§3.4). The inability of an agentic model to accurately assess its own knowledge and decide when to act, defer, or seek help. Example: spending thousands of tokens “thinking” before answering (2+3).

Viewing these failures through a unified, probabilistic lens (Shah et al., 2020) yields both diagnostic power and actionable direction. When a new failure mode emerges, we can ask: *what is the model’s output distribution, and what distribution should it match?*

Contributions.

1. A **unifying framework** that reveals the shared structure beneath hallucination, homogenization, over-refusal, and reasoning failures (§3; see Figure 1 for a visual overview).
2. A **diagnostic vocabulary** for identifying miscalibration: when failures arise, ask what the model is confident about versus what it should match.
3. A **call to action** for the community: calibration metrics should become standard in benchmark reporting, and we outline concrete steps for researchers, developers, and practitioners (§5).

2. What Is Calibration?

Pre-LLMs. In traditional supervised learning, research has extensively covered uncertainty and calibration, with less emphasis on direct confidence estimation. A model’s *confidence* is typically defined as the softmax probability assigned to a predicted class (Nixon et al., 2019; Corbière et al., 2019). Because the output belongs to a fixed, enumerable set, extracting confidence is straightforward. Consequently, prior research has primarily focused on calibration

methods to align predicted probabilities with empirical accuracy. Prominent examples include Platt scaling (Platt et al., 1999), isotonic regression (Niculescu-Mizil & Caruana, 2005), and temperature scaling (Guo et al., 2017).

Generative LLM Context. The advent of generative LLMs necessitates a broader definition of calibration, as they produce free-form text lacking natural single-class probabilities. Confidence estimation in this setting is complicated by three primary factors. First, *semantic equivalence* means that multiple distinct strings can represent the same underlying answer (Kuhn et al., 2023; Zhang et al., 2024a). Second, *alignment distortions* arise because token probabilities are frequently skewed by decoding strategies and RLHF (Achiam et al., 2023; Tian et al., 2023; Kadavath et al., 2022). Finally, the *intractable output space*, which grows exponentially with sequence length, precludes normalizing probabilities over all possible correct answers (Zhang et al., 2025b). These challenges motivate our work in Section 3, where we propose a broader taxonomy of miscalibration that seeks to capture diverse failure modes.

Confidence vs. Uncertainty. We distinguish two oft-conflated concepts: **confidence** estimates the probability that a *specific answer* is correct (guiding acceptance and ranking), while **uncertainty** measures the dispersion of beliefs over *all possible answers* (guiding abstention and tool use) (Lin et al., 2024; Zhang et al., 2024a). Both can be miscalibrated; our framework addresses both. Formal definitions appear in §C.

3. A Framework for LLM Miscalibration

We propose viewing LLM deficiencies through four lenses of miscalibration, each revealing a different aspect of the gap between model confidence and reality. These are not mutually exclusive and could co-occur in practice.

3.1. Probabilistic Miscalibration: The Illusion of Randomness

Probabilistic Miscalibration

The model’s output distribution $q_{\theta}(y | x)$ fails to match a target distribution $p^*(y | x)$ specified in the prompt.

Calibration, at its core, is about matching probabilities to empirical frequencies. Here, the model fails to enact the very probabilities it can correctly describe.

The Problem. The model’s generated distribution of outputs fails to match the target distribution $p^*(y | x)$ described in the prompt. This can be conceptualized as a high divergence between the empirical distribution of samples from q_{θ} and the specified p^* (e.g., KL-divergence). This matters beyond simple queries: stochastic agent policies, best-of-N

generation, and Monte Carlo uncertainty estimation all depend on accurate sampling. When the model cannot match a specified distribution, downstream systems inherit systematic bias.

Random Number Generation. Models cannot reliably produce random numbers. When prompted for a single uniformly random integer, aligned models display a strong preference for “7,” a well-documented psychological bias in humans (Simon, 1971; West & Potts, 2025). Similarly, Zhang et al. (2024b) found Llama-2-13B-chat assigns over 60% of its probability mass to the number “5” when prompted for a random number between 1 and 10, and Mistral-7B-Instruct chooses the name “Avery” 40 times more often than we would expect based on the U.S. population.

Sequential Sampling. This miscalibration extends to sequences. Aligned models exhibit an aversion to repetition that mirrors the human gambler’s fallacy, i.e., the belief that randomness means outcomes are conditional and alternate with some regularity (e.g., after three times red, the next roulette roll is bound to be black). However, a truly random process can contain long sequences of repeated outcomes. For aligned models, the most common outcome (the mode) is a sequence with *zero* repetitions, a significant deviation from any true random sample (West & Potts, 2025).

Knowledge-Behavior Gap. Most tellingly, the previous behavior reveals a schism between a model’s declarative knowledge and its sampling behavior. A model explicitly prompted with the ground truth of a biased coin (e.g., $P(\text{Heads}) = 0.7$) will accurately *verbalize* this probability if asked, yet its internal log-probabilities used for sampling remain highly un-calibrated and fail to match the provided fact (Meister et al., 2025; Kirchhof et al., 2025). The model can describe probability, but cannot enact it. This gap undermines any downstream system that relies on verbalized probabilities as a proxy for sampling behavior.

3.2. Semantic Miscalibration: The Confidence-Factuality Gap

Semantic Miscalibration

The model’s expressed confidence does not reflect the factual correctness of its claims.

This lens moves beyond distribution shapes to examine the correctness of generated content. The core question: when a model sounds confident, should we believe it?

The Problem. When faced with queries beyond its knowledge, a well-calibrated model should express uncertainty. Instead, current models often exhibit overconfidence in incorrect answers and underconfidence in correct ones (Sung et al., 2025).

Root Causes. The prevailing evaluation paradigms rely on binary right-or-wrong scoring, systematically rewarding guessing over expressing uncertainty (Kalai et al., 2025). Even techniques like RLVR degrade calibration due to binary rewards (Damani et al., 2025). This is compounded by a training dilemma: teaching “I don’t know” risks models withholding knowledge they possess, while training only on correct answers forces guessing (Schulman, 2023).

Hallucination. The most direct manifestation of semantic miscalibration is hallucination, a phenomenon that almost every user of an LLM has some level of experience of, and an issue that persists despite significant model advancements (Zhang et al., 2025e). This failure is evident across different evaluation methodologies. On SimpleQA, a benchmark of short factual questions, frontier models achieve accuracies around 50% (Wei et al., 2024; OpenAI, 2025; Comanici et al., 2025). This is not merely a capability limit: the original study finds that models consistently overstate their confidence, with stated confidence exceeding actual accuracy across all models tested (Wei et al., 2024). This problem extends to long-form generation, where LLMs often fail to mark uncertain facts within extended outputs (Yang et al., 2025b;a; Band et al., 2024). Reinforcement-learning methods that encourage explicit uncertainty expressions can mitigate the problem, but they do not eliminate it (Zhang et al., 2025c; Band et al., 2024). Overall, a large gap remains between what models know and how faithfully they communicate what they do not know.

High-Stakes Domains. Semantic miscalibration carries severe consequences in domains where errors cause direct harm. In healthcare, frontier models hallucinate in 23.4% of medical reasoning tasks, yet express high confidence even on these incorrect claims (Kim et al., 2025). This miscalibration compounds with data frequency: models hallucinate more on rare conditions with sparse training coverage (Zhao et al., 2024), precisely where clinical expertise is most critical. Other high-stakes fields, such as the legal domain, face parallel risks, with models fabricating case citations and financial data while maintaining unwarranted confidence (Dahl et al., 2024; Magesh et al., 2025).

Presumptive Grounding. Semantic miscalibration extends to pragmatic failures. LLMs frequently assume shared context that does not exist, being three times less likely than humans to seek clarification (Shaikh et al., 2025). This reflects miscalibration of the model’s theory of mind: it overestimates the probability that its interpretation of user intent is correct. The extreme case is sycophancy, where models abandon their own knowledge to agree with incorrect user premises, miscalibrating their confidence in the user’s correctness over their own (Sharma et al., 2024).

3.3. Distributional Miscalibration: The Collapse of Diversity

Distributional Miscalibration

The model collapses the space of valid outputs into a narrow, stereotypical mode.

While semantic miscalibration focuses on the correctness of a single output \hat{y} , distributional miscalibration concerns the properties of the entire predictive distribution $q_\theta(y | x)$.

The Problem. Many common use cases for LLMs—from creative writing and summarization to product recommendation and advice-seeking—are inherently underspecified and subjective. Instead of having a single correct answer y , there exists a distribution over valid responses that reflects the diversity of human preferences and perspectives. Distributional miscalibration occurs when the model’s output distribution $q_\theta(y | x)$ fails to accurately represent this diversity. Some prior work refers to this as “generative monoculture”: a significant narrowing of output diversity relative to the variety present in the source data (Wu et al., 2025). A common failure mode is when $q_\theta(y | x)$ concentrates probability mass on the most common or prototypical responses while underrepresenting less frequent but equally valid alternatives. In other words, the model captures the central tendency of acceptable responses but fails to represent their full range.

Reduced Novelty. In the domain of language and creativity, miscalibration manifests as a collapse in lexical and semantic diversity. For example, on NoveltyBench, current state-of-the-art LLMs produce significantly fewer unique and novel outputs compared to human writers (Zhang et al., 2025d). This finding is corroborated by large-scale analyses of “epistemic diversity,” which demonstrate that LLMs generate a narrower range of real-world claims than a simple web search (Wright et al., 2025). Crucially, both lines of research converge on a somewhat counter-intuitive scaling property: larger models can exhibit less diversity than their smaller counterparts. Furthermore, Zhang et al. (2025d) trace the root of this problem, showing that each successive stage of alignment, from supervised fine-tuning to preference optimization, progressively reduces a model’s output diversity. This finding suggests the very processes intended to make models more useful are simultaneously making them more uniform.

Clichés and Flattened Identity. When the distribution concerns people, this miscalibration hardens into cliché. Children’s stories generated for non-Western contexts frequently fixate on orientalist tropes, erasing the diverse reality of modern cultures (Rooein et al., 2025). Similarly, recent work identifies “echoes” in narrative generation, quantifying a severe lack of plot diversity compared to humans (Xu et al., 2025). In recommendation and interaction, this tendency

“flattens” identity groups by collapsing a wide spectrum of valid possibilities into a narrow, stereotypically-associated mode (Wang et al., 2025a). For instance, when a user implicitly reveals their race as Black while asking for college recommendations, models disproportionately suggest Historically Black Colleges and Universities (HBCUs), failing to represent the vast range of institutions that would be considered by a human advisor (Kantharuban et al., 2025).

Opinion Homogenization. This failure extends to representing human subjectivity. Instruction-tuning improves a model’s ability to predict consensus views but actively harms its ability to capture pluralistic, high-entropy disagreements (Hu et al., 2025a). This leads to the “correct answer” effect, where models respond to nuanced survey questions about politics and morality with near-zero variation, effectively hallucinating a consensus where none exists (Park et al., 2024). Even when a query is ambiguous (e.g., “What book should I read next?”), models default to a single interpretation—often aligned with a WEIRD context (Henrich et al., 2010)—rather than representing the diversity of possible user needs (Malaviya et al., 2025). For generative tasks with many valid answers, a well-calibrated model should distribute its probability mass across multiple good sequences rather than collapsing to a single mode (Sorensen et al., 2024; Flores et al., 2025).

3.4. Metacognitive Miscalibration: The Failure of Self-Awareness

Metacognitive Miscalibration

The model’s self-assessment of competence is misaligned with its actual capability.

The previous forms of miscalibration concerned the final output content. Metacognitive miscalibration concerns the model’s internal self-assessment: the alignment between its confidence in its own capabilities and its actual performance.

The Problem. A well-calibrated model should “know what it knows”: accurately estimating when it has sufficient knowledge to answer directly versus when it should use a tool, defer to a human, or refuse to answer. Current models often fail at this self-assessment. They cannot reliably distinguish between tasks within versus beyond their competence, leading to both overconfident errors (hallucinating when they should abstain) and underconfident inefficiencies (invoking tools for trivial tasks). This miscalibration of self-awareness undermines the operational decisions that agentic systems must make, from tool use to safety filtering to multi-step reasoning.

Miscalibration in Tool Use. The decision to consult an external tool versus relying on parametric memory is a quintessential metacognitive challenge for agentic LLMs:

the model must estimate its own confidence in answering directly and compare it to the expected utility of external retrieval. A well-calibrated model’s “tool use decision boundary” should align with its actual “knowledge boundary” (Wang et al., 2025b). Miscalibration leads to two costly failure modes. An overconfident model neglects tools even when necessary, particularly for tasks requiring real-time information or precise arithmetic (Wang et al., 2025b). Conversely, an underconfident model engages in tool overuse, unnecessarily invoking external tools for tasks solvable with its own knowledge, incurring significant latency and computational overhead (Qian et al., 2025). This inefficiency is not benign: the accumulation of minor errors from tool interactions can degrade overall task performance (Patil et al., 2024). The problem is further compounded by fragile tool selection, where models are often swayed by superficial phrasing in tool descriptions rather than actual functionality (Faghih et al., 2025). These issues collectively point to a core deficit in “decision calibration”: a misalignment between a model’s confidence in a chosen action and the actual utility of that choice (Liu et al., 2024a).

Miscalibration in Safety Systems. Deployed models make constant decisions about whether a prompt is safe to answer. Conceptually, this decision is governed by an internal, often implicit, estimate of the probability of harm, $p(\text{harm}|x)$. A pervasive failure in modern LLMs is over-refusal (also termed “overkill” or “false refusal”), where this probability is miscalibrated too high, causing the model to be overconfident that a benign prompt is harmful (Cui et al., 2025; Zhang et al., 2025f). This brittleness reveals a flawed and poorly calibrated understanding of risk, which often stems from a superficial analysis that relies on verbal shortcuts, becoming overly sensitive to specific keywords (e.g., ‘kill’) regardless of the safe context (Shi et al., 2024). The challenge is further compounded by the need for user-specific safety, as the true $p(\text{harm})$ is conditioned on the user’s profile: a query that is safe for the general population may be harmful to a vulnerable individual, a dimension where current models are shown to fail profoundly (In et al., 2025).

The miscalibration in safety systems harms user experience and cripples the model’s utility. Research shows that users find simplistic, direct refusals highly frustrating and strongly prefer more nuanced strategies like “diverting denials” or “partial compliance,” where the model provides helpful, even if non-actionable, information instead of a complete stonewall (Wester et al., 2024; Zheng et al., 2025). The challenge is not to simply lower the safety threshold, which compromises safety against genuinely malicious attacks (Cui et al., 2025), but to build better-calibrated safety systems that can make nuanced risk evaluations about the prompt, context, and user.

Miscalibration in Reasoning. Models systematically mis-

judge the quality of their own reasoning. When given the correct first step, they can solve problems they otherwise fail, revealing they possess the capability but cannot accurately assess which reasoning path to take (Jain et al., 2025). This same calibration failure produces “unfaithful reasoning”: models arrive at correct answers via logically flawed rationales, unable to recognize that their stated justification does not match their internal computation (Yee et al., 2024; Zhang et al., 2025a). Nor can they identify errors when flawed rationales are provided in-context, confirming they lack the self-monitoring needed to catch mistakes in their own logic (Zhou et al., 2024b).

This miscalibration extends to assessing problem difficulty, where models expend vast computational resources on trivial tasks (e.g., using nearly 1,000 tokens to answer “2+3=?”) (Chen et al., 2025). In agentic settings, this issue leads to a reasoning–action dilemma: higher “overthinking scores” paradoxically correlate with lower task completion on benchmarks like SWE-bench-Verified, while selecting less-overthought solutions can improve success rates by 30% and cut compute costs by 43% (Cuadron et al., 2025).

At a mechanistic level, this issue is linked to how models handle uncertainty. A well-calibrated reasoner would treat points of low confidence as opportunities for exploration. These decision points often correspond to high-entropy “forking tokens” (e.g., however, alternatively), which signal a potential shift in the logical chain (Cheng et al., 2025). However, standard reinforcement learning techniques tend to suppress these crucial, often low-probability, “reasoning sparks.” This suppression stifles exploration and funnels the model down a single reasoning path with unwarranted confidence (Huang et al., 2025).

This miscalibration makes popular inference-time enhancement strategies less effective and computationally inefficient. For instance, while fine-tuning improves a model’s accuracy on a single reasoning attempt (Pass@1), it can cause “diversity collapse,” harming its ability to find the correct answer when given multiple attempts (Pass@K) (Dang et al., 2025; Hamid et al., 2025). Self-consistency techniques, which rely on sampling diverse reasoning paths, become ineffective when the model produces only narrow variations of the same flawed logic.

Calibration Decay in Long Interactions.

Metacognitive calibration is not static; it erodes over long interactions (Zhang et al., 2026). A model’s expressed confidence remains high even as its effective access to conversational history degrades. This stems partially from attention failure: Liu et al. (2024b) demonstrate a “lost in the middle” effect, where a model’s ability to retrieve information decays based on its position in the context window. In multi-turn dialogue, this manifests as a “loss-in-middle-turns” effect,

where models overweight initial and recent exchanges while forgetting crucial context from the middle (Laban et al., 2025). The failure is that models are not calibrated to their attentional blind spots—they operate with certainty misaligned with their decaying ability to access the full history. This leads to “logical decay” (Lei et al., 2025), where models confidently contradict facts stated turns prior. It also explains why models that take a wrong turn get “lost and do not recover” (Laban et al., 2025): miscalibrated self-assessment prevents them from recognizing their own error.

4. Alternative Views

View 1: These Four Facets Are Separate Problems. A natural objection is that the four facets of miscalibration are fundamentally distinct phenomena with different root causes. In this view, probabilistic miscalibration stems from the model mimicking human cognitive biases absorbed from training data. Semantic miscalibration arises from knowledge gaps and the inability to distinguish memorized facts from plausible confabulations. Distributional miscalibration is a direct artifact of preference optimization, which explicitly selects single “best” responses. Metacognitive miscalibration reflects a lack of explicit self-monitoring training. Each problem, this view argues, has domain-specific solutions that work in isolation: retrieval-augmented generation for hallucination, higher sampling temperatures for diversity, better safety classifiers for over-refusal. The logical endpoint of this view is architectural separation: train specialized models for each domain (a safety model, a factual QA model, a creative generation model), each optimized for its specific calibration challenge, with a routing system directing queries appropriately.

We argue that these targeted solutions are *patches*, not cures: bandages applied to symptoms rather than treatments addressing the disease causing them. Consider the pattern: RAG reduces hallucination by offloading factual recall to an external database, but the model’s *internal* confidence remains miscalibrated; it cannot distinguish what it knows from what it retrieved. Temperature scaling increases output diversity, but artificially. It does not teach the model which queries warrant diverse responses versus which have unique correct answers. Safety classifiers reduce over-refusal by adding an external filter, but the model itself still lacks a calibrated sense of risk.

The specialized models approach merely elevates the problem: the routing system itself must now be calibrated about which model to invoke—a metacognitive calibration challenge. Moreover, it presupposes that queries neatly partition into domains, when real-world prompts often span multiple facets simultaneously (e.g., “Write a creative but factually accurate story about Marie Curie”). Most critically, each specialized model would still exhibit all four facets of mis-

calibration within its domain. A “safety specialist” can still be probabilistically miscalibrated about risk distributions, semantically miscalibrated about what constitutes harm, distributionally miscalibrated in collapsing to over-cautious defaults, and metacognitively miscalibrated about when to escalate to human review. In each case, the intervention works around the model’s flawed uncertainty representation rather than fixing it.

Nor do external filters and guardrails, the dominant paradigm in production systems, escape this issue. A hallucination detector must be calibrated about what constitutes a factual error. A safety filter must be calibrated about risk thresholds. Whether the calibration problem lives in the main model or in external components, it remains unsolved. This is why the same failure modes persistently resurface in new forms: conformity (Zhu et al., 2025), sycophancy (Sharma et al., 2024), overthinking (Chen et al., 2025; Cuadron et al., 2025), mode collapse (Dang et al., 2025), lost-in-the-middle (Laban et al., 2025). Like whack-a-mole, each requires a new bespoke patch because we never addressed the underlying deficit.

Our unified framing does *not* claim that one solution will fix all four facets. Rather, it argues that all four share a common root: the model’s inability to accurately represent its own uncertainty. Sustainable progress requires targeting this root rather than endlessly patching its manifestations.

View 2: Model Progress Will Naturally Fix Miscalibration. A second objection holds that miscalibration is just a temporary limitation that will dissolve as models improve. We should focus research effort on advancing the capability frontier; calibration will follow. So far, each generation of LLMs is indeed more capable than the last: better at reasoning, more factually accurate, more instruction-following. From this perspective, calibration will naturally improve as a byproduct of capability gains.

Existing evidence contradicts this view. The relationship between capability and calibration is not monotonic. Cao et al. (2025) show that across models ranging from 0.5B to 70B parameters, larger models are no better calibrated than smaller ones: they accumulate errors during generation at essentially the same rate regardless of scale. This occurs because natural language follows a power law distribution with an exponent close to 1, which theoretically predicts negligible calibration gains from scaling. Larger models can also exhibit less diversity, and alignment stages progressively degrade calibration (see §3.3) (Wright et al., 2025; Zhang et al., 2025d). The evidence suggests that current scaling and alignment paradigms do not naturally produce calibrated models; if anything, they may exacerbate certain forms of miscalibration. This is precisely why we argue for calibration as a primary evaluation target: without explicit measurement and optimization pressure, capability gains

will continue to mask or worsen calibration failures.

View 3: Perfect Calibration May Be Undesirable. Finally, one might argue that some degree of overconfidence is *functional*. For many applications, maximizing Pass@1 accuracy is the only metric that matters: the user wants the single best answer, not a distribution of hedged possibilities. Furthermore, user studies show that people often prefer confident, direct responses (Wester et al., 2024), and hedging can be perceived as evasive or unhelpful.

This argument conflates two distinct concerns. The first is that whether Pass@1 is the right objective is application-dependent. We readily concede that for some use cases, optimizing single-shot accuracy is appropriate. But this use is precisely why calibration matters: a well-calibrated model enables *informed* deployment decisions. System designers need the confidence signal to decide when to present a single answer versus multiple options, when to route to human review, or when to invoke external tools. If the model cannot produce reliable uncertainty estimates, these choices become impossible. The second concern is: how to present uncertainty to users is a system-level UX decision. It presupposes we have access to meaningful confidence signals in the first place. We must solve the ML problem (extracting accurate confidence) before the interface design problem (presenting it effectively) can even be posed. Our position is not that all deployments should display uncertainty, but that all models should *have* calibrated uncertainty available as a primitive for downstream system design.

5. From Capabilities to Reliability: A Research Agenda

Reframing disparate LLM failures as facets of miscalibration provides a unified lens, but it also surfaces fundamental challenges that cannot be solved by isolated patches. We outline four critical areas where progress is needed to move from merely capable models to genuinely reliable systems.

Measure: A Call for Calibrated Benchmarking For model developers, calibration was once an important metric; the GPT-4 report, for instance, featured detailed calibration curves (Achiam et al., 2023). Yet, as the field has raced toward maximizing aggregate benchmarks, this practice has quietly disappeared - no subsequent major model releases have mentioned calibration. We face a transparency crisis: while community leaderboards meticulously track accuracy (Pass@1), they almost entirely ignore calibration.

This creates a blind spot regarding model reliability. Accuracy alone cannot distinguish a well-calibrated model—which correctly assesses its uncertainty and assigns high confidence to correct answers and low confidence to incorrect ones—from a miscalibrated one that achieves high

accuracy through overconfident convergence on narrow reasoning paths. A model that scores 90% on a benchmark while being equally confident in its correct and incorrect answers is fundamentally different from one that scores 90% and appropriately expresses uncertainty on the remaining 10%. Without measuring the alignment between confidence and correctness, we cannot determine whether a model genuinely knows when it has the right answer or is merely guessing with unwarranted certainty. This distinction is critical for deployment decisions: a well-calibrated model enables systems to route low-confidence queries to human review, invoke external tools when uncertain, or present multiple options when appropriate.

Breaking this cycle requires action from benchmark developers and the research community alike. Every benchmark evaluation should report calibration metrics (e.g., Expected Calibration Error, Brier scores) alongside accuracy. For generative tasks, diversity metrics such as Self-BLEU or unique n -gram ratios should become standard. Conference reviewers should ask of empirical papers: “*How does this model’s calibration compare to baselines?*”

Looking ahead, the community needs a **holistic calibration benchmark suite** that evaluates the four facets of miscalibration simultaneously. Such a benchmark would not merely check if an answer is right, but would quantify the alignment of confidence scores with correctness (Semantic), measure whether models can enact specified probability distributions (Probabilistic), assess output diversity against human baselines (Distributional), and evaluate the utility of metacognitive decisions like tool use and abstention (Metacognitive). Recent efforts like HELM (Liang et al., 2023) and the Humanity’s Last Exam leaderboard (Scale AI, 2025) point in this direction, but calibration-aware evaluation must become the norm, not the exception. The urgency is real: as LLMs become embedded in high-stakes decision-making tasks such as medical diagnosis and legal research, miscalibration poses immediate, measurable harm that our current evaluation practices actively obscure.

Train: The Alignment-Calibration Trade-off A critical open question is whether our current alignment paradigms are fundamentally incompatible with calibration. Base models are often well-calibrated—their token probabilities reflect genuine uncertainty about what comes next (Achiam et al., 2023). However, alignment techniques like RLHF (Ouyang et al., 2022) typically optimize for a point estimate of goodness, training the model to converge on a single, highly-rated response. This creates an alignment-calibration trade-off: the process of aligning a model to be more helpful and safe systematically degrades its calibration (Hu et al., 2025b).

If post-training is part of the problem, model developers must rethink alignment paradigms. One path forward is

to move beyond point-estimate optimization entirely and explore new frontiers like distributional RL or preference models that reward a portfolio of diverse outputs (Zhou et al., 2025b; Lanchantin et al., 2025), rather than just picking a single winner. Alternatively, instead of creating a single monolithic model that must embody all desired traits, we could embrace the trade-offs of alignment by making use of base models. Recent work has proposed collaborative inference strategies where different model checkpoints from the training pipeline are dynamically selected to generate different segments of a single response (Feng et al., 2025). Model merging techniques offer another avenue, allowing interpolation between base and aligned weights to navigate the helpfulness-calibration trade-off explicitly (Hu et al., 2025b). At minimum, the practice of publishing calibration curves in technical reports should be restored, making the calibration cost of alignment visible and accountable.

Deploy: Rethinking the interaction design Finally, we must address the last mile of miscalibration: the interface. Even a perfectly calibrated model is of limited use if the interaction paradigm acts as an information bottleneck. The dominant chat-based interface forces a lossy compression of the model’s high-dimensional, probabilistic belief state into a single, deterministic token sequence. This fosters an *Illusion of Determinism*; users consistently overestimate model accuracy when denied access to internal uncertainty, failing to adjust their trust even when the model errs (Steyvers et al., 2025). Practitioners deploying LLMs should design interaction paradigms that support *Probabilistic Disclosure*, e.g., visualizing confidence intervals or exposing multiple reasoning paths. An alternative approach is linguistic calibration: training models to express uncertainty through natural language (“I’m confident that...” vs. “I think maybe...”) rather than numeric probabilities (Band et al., 2024; Zhou et al., 2024a). The goal is not to burden users with probability distributions but to ensure that the uncertainty inherent in model outputs reaches the humans who must act on them. Addressing miscalibration requires preserving the signal of uncertainty through the communication channel, from the model’s weights to the human decision-maker.

Sustain: The Synthetic Data Feedback Loop The stakes extend beyond individual deployments to ecosystem-level sustainability. As synthetic data becomes central to training pipelines, miscalibration creates a systemic threat. When models collapse onto narrow, stereotypical outputs, this homogenized text feeds into the next generation of training data, triggering a degenerative feedback loop known as Model Collapse (Shumailov et al., 2024). The long-term solution is to fix calibration at the source: ensuring models used for data generation are distributionally calibrated. In the interim, practitioners can explore diversity-preserving patches during data generation, such as persona-

based sampling (Hu & Collier, 2024; Lambert et al., 2025; Ge et al., 2025), or during distillation, preserving multiple valid reasoning chains rather than collapsing to a single canonical path (Guha et al., 2025). However, these remain symptomatic interventions rather than fundamental fixes. Ultimately, well-calibrated models that maintain diverse, uncertainty-aware outputs are essential not just for today’s deployments but for sustaining the quality of tomorrow’s training data.

Generalize: Calibration in Multimodal Systems While our analysis focuses on text, the four facets of miscalibration apply across modalities. Text-to-image models exhibit severe stereotypical tendencies even for underspecified prompts (e.g., 98% of generated “cookies” sharing the same shape), collapsing the rich distribution of valid visualizations into a narrow default (Rassin et al., 2024). Multimodal LLMs frequently lack the metacognitive self-awareness to distinguish between visible content and unanswerable queries, confidently answering questions not grounded in the image (Wang et al., 2024).

We advocate for a convergence of calibration research across generative modalities. While distinct data modalities have historically necessitated specialized calibration techniques, the emergence of natively multimodal architectures presents a unique opportunity: rather than treating modalities separately, future research should explore methods where the information in one modality (e.g., visual evidence) serves as a calibration signal for another (e.g., textual reasoning).

6. Conclusion

Addressing miscalibration is a prerequisite for trustworthy AI systems. A model incapable of assessing its own uncertainty is a liability, prone to confident errors in high-stakes domains and unable to recognize the boundaries of its competence. The rapid proliferation of agentic systems with tool use and multi-step reasoning makes this especially urgent: an agent that cannot accurately assess when to act, defer, or seek help is not merely unreliable but dangerous.

The field has achieved remarkable capability gains, but capabilities without calibration are a liability. We can build models that score 90% on benchmarks while being equally confident in their correct and incorrect answers—and current evaluation practices cannot tell the difference. This paper argues that calibration must become a primary optimization target, not an afterthought. The good news: base models often start well-calibrated. We do not need to invent calibration from scratch—we need to stop destroying it. The path forward requires rethinking how we train, evaluate, and deploy language models, with uncertainty at the center rather than the margin.

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A. Limitations

The boundaries between our four facets of miscalibration are porous by design; many real-world failures exhibit multiple facets simultaneously (e.g., a hallucinated legal citation reflects both semantic and metacognitive miscalibration). Our framework is intended as a diagnostic lens, not a strict taxonomy. Our critique of alignment methods like RLHF highlights their potential to exacerbate certain forms of miscalibration, but we acknowledge their substantial benefits for instruction-following and safety. The precise relationship between alignment objectives, output diversity, and calibration metrics remains an open empirical question requiring systematic investigation beyond the scope of this position paper. Finally, while we argue for the importance of calibration, we do not claim that perfect calibration is always achievable or even desirable across all deployment contexts—the appropriate level of calibration depends on task requirements and user needs.

B. Ethical Considerations

The central theme of this paper—the unreliability of current LLMs—has significant ethical implications. **Semantic miscalibration** leads to the confident spread of misinformation. **Distributional miscalibration** amplifies social stereotypes and marginalizes underrepresented groups. **Metacognitive miscalibration** in safety systems can lead to over-refusal, denying users access to legitimate information, or under-refusal, failing to prevent harm. By providing a unified framework, we hope to encourage research into more robust and reliable models. It is crucial that the “calibrated benchmarks” we call for are developed with diverse stakeholders to ensure they measure reliability across different cultural contexts and demographic groups.

C. Formal Notation and Definitions

We make the following formal distinctions from “classical” supervised learning in our four concepts.

1. **Confidence Estimation:** Assigns a score $s(x, a) \in [0, 1]$ to each question–answer pair (x, a) interpreting the estimated probability that answer a is *correct* for question x .
2. **Uncertainty Estimation:** Quantifies the dispersion of the model’s predictive belief *about possible answers* given x , independent of any single answer a .
3. **Calibration Methods:** Procedures that transform raw confidence scores to improve alignment, either post hoc or during training.
4. **Calibration Level:** A property describing how well (possibly scaled) confidence scores align with empirical correctness.

Notation. Let \mathcal{X} be the input space and \mathcal{Y} the output space (token sequences, classes, spans, etc.). A model with parameters θ induces a predictive distribution $q_\theta(a | x)$ and a task-specific point prediction $\hat{a}(x) \in \mathcal{Y}$. For tasks admitting an automatic checker or oracle, define the correctness indicator

$$C(x, a) \in \{0, 1\},$$

which returns 1 iff answer a is correct for input x . For a dataset $\mathcal{D} = \{x_i\}_{i=1}^n$, we write $[n] = \{1, \dots, n\}$.

Why Confidence and Uncertainty Matter. Confidence answers “*how likely is this specific answer a to be correct for x ?*”, guiding acceptance, ranking, and aggregation of model outputs. Uncertainty answers “*how stable are the model’s beliefs over answers for x ?*”, guiding *when* to trust the model at all—e.g., abstention, human routing, tool use, or clarification—especially in open-ended LLM settings where a calibrated correctness probability may be unavailable.

Confidence Estimation. A confidence estimation method is a function $s : \mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{Y} \rightarrow [0, 1]$ such that

$$s(x, a) \approx \Pr(C(x, a) = 1 | x, a).$$

A common practical choice evaluates the actual predicted answer $\hat{a}(x)$ because downstream decisions act on the single deployed output, and computing correctness for all $a \in \mathcal{Y}$ is impractical:

$$s(x, \hat{a}(x)) \approx \Pr(C(x, \hat{a}(x)) = 1 | x, \hat{a}(x)).$$

In multiclass classification, $s(x, \hat{a}(x))$ is often the top-label probability $q_\theta(\hat{a}(x) | x)$. However, because LLMs generate high-dimensional, free-form text, simple token probabilities often fail to capture true confidence. This necessitates alternative estimation strategies, such as by (i) prompting for verbalized confidence (Tian et al., 2023; Xiong et al., 2024), or (ii) sampling multiple candidates and mapping semantic

consistency to a correctness probability proxy (Manakul et al., 2023).

Uncertainty Estimation Let $q_\theta(a \mid x)$ be the model’s predictive distribution over answers $a \in \mathcal{Y}$ for input x . **Uncertainty** is any score that depends only on $q_\theta(\cdot \mid x)$ (and not on a specific answer). We write

$$u(x) = f(q_\theta(\cdot \mid x)),$$

where $u(x)$ need not be in $[0, 1]$. Meanwhile, $u(x)$ is *not* a probability that the model’s chosen answer is correct. It is used to rank inputs by risk or difficulty (e.g., abstain or route to a human), and is typically evaluated with discrimination metrics such as AUROC/AUPRC rather than calibration error (Lin et al., 2024; Kuhn et al., 2023).

Calibration Methods Raw confidence scores are often miscalibrated. **Calibration methods** learn a calibrator $h : [0, 1] \rightarrow [0, 1]$ on held-out data and apply it at test time to achieve better calibration level:

$$s'(x, a) = h(s(x, a))$$

Post-hoc approaches include temperature scaling and isotonic regression; calibration can also be promoted during training (e.g., via loss design or data augmentation).

Calibration Level Calibration level quantifies the alignment between *confidence scores* and *empirical correctness*. Raw scores from confidence estimation are often transformed via calibration methods to optimize this metric. Formally, let $S = s(X, A)$ denote a scalar confidence score, typically evaluated at the model’s prediction $A = \hat{a}(X)$. Perfect calibration requires that for all $t \in [0, 1]$:

$$\Pr(C = 1 \mid S = t) = t.$$

Empirically, this property is visualized using *reliability diagrams* and measured by metrics such as Expected Calibration Error (ECE), Maximum Calibration Error (MCE), and Brier Score.

Summary In this paper, we use *calibration level* to denote calibration as a property, and *calibration method* to denote calibration as a procedure (Zhou et al., 2025a). Thus, a strong *confidence estimator* combined with an effective *calibration method* is a practical way to improve *calibration level*. Unless stated otherwise, we use “calibration” and “miscalibration” to refer to calibration level.